

CERTIFICATE

OF APPRECIATION

TIBBIYOT AKADEMIYASI

JURNALIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Karshiyeva Dilovar Rustamovna

SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF ORAL FLUID COMPOSITION OF SMOKERS

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI

WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

